

K7NC STATION PHOTOGRAPH

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To: hamsci.seqp@gmail.com

Re: HamSCI 2024 GSSC Entry

From: Jim Boardman K7NC, Grid CN87sm, North End of Vashon Island WA, USA

Description (photo is a bit too blurry to read equipment IDs)

- Top row, Left to Right
 - Kenwood R-599D receiver, Kenwood T-599D transmitter (“Kenwood Twins”)
 - Heathkit HM-2140 1.8 – 30 MHz SWR/Power Meter, resting on...
 - PYLE PCA3 Stereo Power Amplifier
 - Computer monitor (partial view)
- 2nd row from top, Left to Right
 - Yaesu FP-1030A Power Supply (partial view) then my call sign label (with CN87sm grid loc)
 - Kenwood R-5000 receiver (with the VC-20 VHF Converter)
 - Scarlett 616 Audio interface (connects to Focusrite application on Windows 10), resting on...
 - Yaesu FTdx10 (tuned to 20 Meters WSPR band)
 - Heathkit IM-103 Line Voltage Monitor
- Bottom row, Left to Right
 - My favorite coffee cup and the FTdx10 hand microphone
 - A custom wood call sign desk plaque
 - Vibroplex “Vibrokeyer Deluxe” keyer with Vibroplex dust cover
 - Antique camel hair phono record dust brush

